

CONSTRUCTION AND PRACTICE OF BLENDED TEACHING IN COLLEGE ENGLISH BASED ON FLIPPED CLASSROOM

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Abstract. The implementation of a blended instructional approach incorporating the flipped classroom model plays a crucial role in enhancing College English education, improving teaching effectiveness, and fostering students' English learning. Blended instruction integrates conventional face-to-face teaching with online learning resources. At the same time, the flipped classroom serves as a primary means of achieving this hybrid learning format. This paper explores the development of a new integrated teaching method based on the flipped classroom model and examines its application to support the advancement of College English education.

Keywords: blended teaching, college english, flipped classroom

Annotatsiya. Aralash ta'lim yondashuvini amalga oshirish, fliplangan sinf modelini o'z ichiga olgan holda, Kollej ingliz tili ta'limini rivojlantirishda, o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda va talabalar ingliz tili o'rganishini rag'batlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Aralash ta'lim an'anaviy to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'qitishni onlayn ta'lim resurslari bilan birlashtiradi. Shu bilan birga, fliplangan sinf bu aralash ta'lim formatini amalga oshirishning asosiy vositasi sifatida xizmat qiladi. Ushbu maqola fliplangan sinf modeliga asoslangan yangi integratsiyalangan o'qitish metodining rivojlanishini o'rganadi va uning Kollej ingliz tili ta'limini rivojlantirishga yordam berishini tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: aralash ta'lim, kollej ingliz tili, fliplangan sinf

Аннотация. Реализация подхода смешанного обучения с использованием модели перевернутого класса играет ключевую роль в улучшении образования по английскому языку в колледжах, повышении эффективности преподавания и содействии обучению студентов английскому языку. Смешанное обучение сочетает традиционное очное преподавание с онлайн-ресурсами для обучения. В то же время, перевернутый класс служит основным инструментом для реализации этого гибридного формата обучения. В данной статье рассматривается разработка нового интегрированного метода преподавания на основе модели перевернутого класса и анализируется его применение для поддержки развития образования по английскому языку в колледже.

Ключевые слова: смешанное обучение, колледжский английский, перевернутый класс.

Introduction. In the modern era, technology is advancing rapidly, and the application of big data is becoming increasingly widespread. With the continuous updates to the new college English curriculum, blended teaching emerges as an innovative instructional approach. Rather than completely rejecting previous teaching experiences and models, it builds upon them through critique and refinement. In general, blended teaching maximizes the use of internet resources and information technology while integrating with flipped classroom English teaching methods. At its core, flipped classroom English teaching thoroughly considers students' real-life contexts, aiming to enrich their life experiences and deepen their understanding by implementing instructional activities that emphasize practical skill development. This approach ultimately enhances students' English proficiency.

On a deeper level, incorporating flipped classroom English teaching into college courses aligns well with the pedagogical principles introduced in the new curriculum reform. Specifically, educators utilizing this method guide students through reading and writing exercises connected to their personal experiences, which enhances their awareness of life and enriches their emotional intelligence. Moreover, by linking English learning with life experiences, students engage in listening, speaking, reading, and writing tasks in an emotionally driven manner rather than focusing solely on linguistic mechanics.

With the swift progression of information technology in the age of big data, computers and digital networks have become essential tools in college English education. Traditional teaching methods no longer satisfy contemporary demands, necessitating a reevaluation of college English instruction. The shift from a teacher-centered classroom to a student-focused interactive discussion model is becoming increasingly urgent. Simultaneously, in an era that promotes lifelong learning, the significance of online autonomous learning is becoming more evident. When interactive classroom instruction is integrated with independent online learning, a hybrid teaching approach naturally takes shape, and share them with other teachers after sorting out. On top of the above-mentioned measures, to offer supplementary aids, the competent education department can speed up the establishment of education and teaching resources to support English teaching according to the core curriculum.

The conventional teaching approach primarily focuses on memorizing vocabulary, spelling, completing reading exercises, and developing listening and speaking skills. However, it does not adequately emphasize language communication and real-world application. As a result, many students still struggle with practical language use, often becoming passive learners with limited speaking proficiency. Existing teaching methods often fail to cultivate students' cross-cultural communication skills. Most college English classes still rely heavily on teacher-centered lectures, with students passively listening rather than actively engaging. This approach limits students' participation and reduces meaningful interaction. Additionally, cross-cultural competence remains largely theoretical, with minimal cultural awareness integrated into the curriculum. Instructors tend to focus solely on textbook content while neglecting the importance of guiding students to understand Western cultural contexts. College English education should go beyond language acquisition, incorporating cultural elements through comparative analysis to help students gain a deeper understanding of Western traditions and values. Traditional classroom settings often create a dull and uninspiring learning environment, leading to low student engagement. Due to large class sizes, educators frequently adopt a "one-size-fits-all" teaching method, prioritizing content delivery over student comprehension. This results in an overwhelming number of topics being covered without ensuring that students fully grasp the material. Consequently, the classroom atmosphere becomes monotonous, causing students to lose interest and become disengaged. Blended learning primarily refers to an instructional approach that combines traditional face-to-face classroom teaching with digital and online distance education. This method not only maintains the teacher's central role in guiding classroom instruction but also encourages students to actively engage in the learning process.

Materials and methods.

The flipped classroom is an innovative teaching strategy where educators provide students with learning materials, often in video format, through an online learning platform. This allows students to review course content before attending class and come prepared with questions for discussion. Within a flipped classroom setting, students are encouraged to explore new concepts, exchange perspectives, and engage in collaborative discussions. The core idea is to position students as the focal point of classroom activities, promoting their active involvement in the learning process. This approach represents a modern hybrid learning model. By integrating visual and auditory tools with traditional lecture-based instruction in college English courses, the flipped classroom has significantly enhanced students' enthusiasm for learning, self-motivation, and proficiency in English listening and speaking. The development of this model should adhere to three fundamental principles:

1. Equal emphasis should be placed on both knowledge acquisition and fostering students' interest in learning.
2. A variety of stimulating activities should be incorporated to develop speaking skills, rather than relying solely on oral practice.
3. Language proficiency and cultural awareness should be cultivated simultaneously.

Through the implementation of this approach, it is hoped that a new pathway will be established to drive reforms in college English education.

4. Theoretical Basis

The advantages of traditional teaching methods with the advantages of digital or network learning [6]. To put it another way, it combines with other effective teaching approaches while eliminating unpreferable factors to make classroom teaching diversified. Thus, instructional activities will be conducted in more flexible and creative ways on the basis of blended teaching concepts. According to

scholars' existing researches, the actual benefits brought about by flipped classroom can be listed as follows. To start with, flipped classroom enables students to share the latest knowledge resources through video so that students will be more involved in class. Additionally, flipped classroom reconstructs the structure and mode of traditional teaching, promoting teachers and students to change their roles. As a result, students will be motivated to a greater extent and be more active than they are in a traditional classroom. Moreover, flipped classroom is rather conducive to the cultivation of students' practical ability as well, since students will have to finish tasks that need all-round reflection and involve putting such reflections into practice [7]. On the other hand, it is the content of the course that is altered and shifted in a tremendous way under such learning circumstance. Since the course content will be presented in the form of micro videos, learners can achieve English proficiency, communicative skills and multiple culture awareness input simultaneously.

Another advantageous element of flipped classroom, mentioned in a wide range of relevant literatures, is the style of adopting micro class. Micro class, which is an instructional approach that employs three-dimensional short video clips consuming no more than 10 minutes to present essential course contents, condenses the knowledge points and makes an in-depth and thorough analysis on required knowledge points with multiple aids such as images, recordings and visual materials. Students' own learning experience will be increased and their interest in English learning will be enormously provoked in the process of producing micro class materials. In the three-dimensional short video clips of micro class, language and culture input are integrated to make the theme of the target unit more specific and clearer. In terms of course contents, in addition to completing the teaching tasks detailed in college English syllabus, instructors can also introduce English learning topics of engaging factors to students such as topics about the latest news, movies, music and popular science via micro class video clips, which will not only broaden students' horizons and stimulate their interest and enthusiasm in learning, but also complete the integration of their thinking channels with those of the instructors more smoothly. Basically, students are able to study micro class videos online or offline autonomously while other learning activities such as taking notes, submitting homework, self-evaluation, peer evaluation and prompt feedback can also be effectively conducted.[8].

In the flipped classroom mode, students can complete their learning tasks before class through video clips without face-to-face instructions. Students will then have more opportunities to participate in other learning activities with the teacher in class. Various methods are interspersed and used flexibly. Students complete tasks or solve problems together through communication and cooperation. Teachers can ask and answer questions promptly, offer overall guidance and specific guidance to help students form new ideas and basic framework for assignments independently. For more complex or common problems, teachers may explain them in detail and combine the traditional teaching with a variety of autonomous learning methods based on the network to form a hybrid teaching method [9].

Teaching materials for flipped classroom mainly cover micro classes, PowerPoint courseware and video clips. During the teaching process, the instructor is to prepare the network, USB flash disk and audio-visual software as the carrier to produce course-related materials, and to get relevant 3 tasks including document editing, micro course production, video shooting and editing, etc. done according to the course content and objectives. Particularly, it is to be noted that the production of "micro class", whose core content is classroom-teaching-based video clips (lesson fragments), includes supplementary teaching resources related to the teaching theme, such as teaching design, material courseware, teaching reflection, practice test, student feedback and teacher comments. The duration of "micro class" is generally about 5-8 minutes, and the maximum should not exceed 10 minutes [10].

By using the platforms of Chuangke, QQ, wechat, scallop, Baici chop and Youdao dictionary, teachers and students are required to make full use of the network to load wechat and other resources onto the app platform, so that the course can be reached anytime and anywhere, and classroom teaching can also be expanded in all three teaching stages -- before, during and after class through the app platform. After completing the blended English teaching in college based on the concept of flipped classroom, in order to consolidate the students' understanding of the content, teachers need to arrange follow-up tasks to enable students to display their knowledge, such as producing PPT courseware, recording corresponding videos and composing learning summaries. Teachers can also upload students' learning achievements to the

network platform through multimedia to realize mutual learning and information exchanging among students and thus improve students' English application ability. To be honest, there are certain restrictive factors in the application of blended teaching methods as well, which are listed as follows: to begin with, students' English proficiency may not reach the expected level and their autonomous learning ability may probably not be ideal; in addition, English teaching conducted in classroom circumstance generally focuses on textbook materials [11], ignoring the application of other teaching resources related to overall teaching; furthermore, English teachers' personal ability level may be limited so that they may fail to employ newly introduced methods.

In order to solve these problems and to better realize the hybrid teaching based on the concept of flipped classroom, teachers need to improve their teaching performance from the following aspects: 1. Teachers should redefine their role orientation. In the process of mixed teaching, teachers function as the guides, supervisors and assistants of students' learning. Therefore, all teaching links have to emphasize students' learning needs and learning objectives. Before class, teachers should provide rich and diverse teaching resources for students. In class, teachers should scientifically design teaching tasks and situations and organize students to carry out group discussions to promote students' understanding and absorption of language points [12]. 2. Teachers should flexibly change teaching methods according to the characteristics of English curriculum and the current situation of students' English proficiency. Based on the integrated concept of flipped classroom, the targeted teaching method takes students' learning as the main goal. As a result, in actual English teaching, teachers should teach students in line with their aptitude, so as to obtain the best effect. 3. Teachers should always polish their teaching skills and comprehensive quality. Universities should regularly organize teachers to participate in various types of further study and professional training so that they are able to systematically acquire the latest teaching concepts, and master more English teaching methods. 4. The construction and sharing of high-quality teaching resources should be achieved. Excellent teaching resources are essential guarantee for supreme teaching effects. Naturally, teachers need to produce teaching courseware according to different teaching requirements. Consequently, teachers can selectively collect and sort out school-based resources, and share them with other teachers after sorting out. On top of the above-mentioned measures, to offer supplementary aids, the competent education department can speed up the establishment of education and teaching resources to support English teaching according to the core curriculum.

Conclusions.

The concept of flipped classroom is based on the comprehensive and online open autonomous learning platform. It advocates the concepts of openness, a-master, personalized learning and inclusiveness, which has strong characteristics in accordance with the demand of the times. The mixed Teaching methods is applied in the field of language teaching. It focuses on cultivating students' language application ability. At the same time, it adopts a variety of language teaching methods to advocate the teaching concept that emphasizes students' leading role. Teachers help students with their exploration, practice and creation to the greatest extent, and encourage them to develop critical thinking and come up with innovative ideas. With the guidance and inspiration of teachers and micro class video serving as the starting point, language learning and culture awareness fostering are both effectively attained. This is not only a brave innovation of teaching methods, but also an innovation of educational science and technology. The mixed teaching method respects the potential of students, and gives students considerable opportunities to explore, discuss, ask questions and criticize themselves, so that they can derive new ideas from team discussions, test the authenticity of knowledge in practice, and learn to explore the dialectical relationship between traditional and innovative learning methods. Teachers functioning as guidance can not only solve doubts, but also absorb students' innovative ideas and they, too, benefit a great deal from such teaching process.

To sum up, in addition to creating new ideas for academic research, the blende teaching method based on flipped classroom is of great value for cultivating cross-border talents as well as innovative talents in the future. It is a future trend to attach great importance to such teaching methods on the way of developing new instructional approaches.

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